

ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT AND HEALTH RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH E-WASTE IN PORT HARCOURT, RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA.

**¹Ogboeli Goodluck Prince, ¹Amos-Bein Ebiere Berly, ¹Kemmer Ibifuro Bapakaye,
²Igbudu Onukwurumege and ³Avwersuo Peace Edile**

¹Institute of Geosciences and Environmental Management, Rivers State University, Nkpolu Oroworukwo, Port
Harcourt

²Department of Science Laboratory Technology, School of Applied Sciences, Kenule Beeson Saro-Wiwa
Polytechnic, Bori

³Department of Environmental Science, Faculty of Sciences, National Open University, Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The rapid increase in the use of electrical and electronic equipment has triggered a surge in e-waste-one of the fastest growing waste streams globally. In Nigeria, informal recycling is predominant due to massive imports of used electronics and weak regulations. This study assessed environmental management practices, radiological hazards effects, and health risks in selected computer villages in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. A mixed-methods cross-sectional design was adopted. We collected data from 150 respondents (100 e-waste workers and 50 nearby residents) using structured questionnaires, a standardized observation checklist (administered over multiple sessions), and key informant interviews with 10 stakeholders. Soil samples (n = 20) were analyzed for natural radionuclides (²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K) using high-purity germanium (HPGe) gamma-ray spectrometry, and radiological hazard indices were calculated following UNSCEAR and ICRP guidelines. Descriptive and inferential statistics (chi-square test, t-test, and analysis of variance) were performed using SPSS version 26.0, with significance set at p < 0.05. Results showed overwhelmingly rudimentary practices: manual dismantling (91.3%–94.0%), open burning (≈80%), mixed storage of hazardous components (86.3%), and extremely low PPE usage (respiratory protection in only 6.5% of observations). On-site dumping and burning are the dominant disposal methods. Soil analysis revealed moderately elevated ²²⁶Ra and ²³²Th levels at active sites compared with the control, with absorbed dose rates, annual effective doses, and excess lifetime cancer risk exceeding world averages at high-intensity burning locations, while other hazard indices remained below international limits. Self-reported health symptoms, including lower back pain (75%), persistent cough/wheezing (68%), cuts/burns (72%), and eye irritation (55%), were highly prevalent among workers. Smoke and dust inhalation (82.7%) was the dominant exposure pathway. Nearby residents also reported notable symptoms, indicating a community-wide exposure. The study concludes that informal e-waste recycling in computer villages in Port Harcourt poses significant environmental and public health risks due to primitive methods and inadequate protection. To mitigate these impacts and promote sustainable e-waste management in the Niger Delta region, it is strongly recommended to strengthen the enforcement of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), provide occupational health training and PPE, implement regular environmental and radiological monitoring, and facilitate a structured transition to formalized recycling systems.

Keywords: Electronic Waste (E-waste), Environmental Impacts, Environmental Pollution, Public Health Risks, Waste Management Practices.

1. Introduction

The exponential growth in the production and consumption of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) has led to a parallel surge in electronic waste (e-waste), also known as WEEE. E-waste comprises discarded devices such as computers, mobile phones, televisions, and refrigerators containing batteries or plugs. These electronic devices harbor hazardous substances, including heavy metals (e.g., lead, cadmium, and mercury), persistent organic pollutants (POPs), such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). E-waste represents one of the fastest-growing waste streams globally. In 2022, a record 62 million tonnes were generated worldwide, equivalent to an average of 7.8 kg per capita, marking an 82% increase from 2010 levels. Only 22.3% of this waste was formally collected and recycled in an environmentally sound manner, with projections indicating a rise to 82 million tonnes by 2030 if current trends persist (Baldé et al., 2024). This rapid escalation outpaces recycling efforts by nearly a factor of 5, worsening environmental degradation and public health threats, particularly in developing regions where informal processing dominates.

In sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, the importation of used EEE from developed countries, often under the guise of bridging the digital divide, amplifies e-waste challenges Nigeria generates approximately 1.1 million tons of WEEE annually, with some estimates estimating 1.2 million tons in recent years. This value increases steadily and receives significant additional volumes through imports, a substantial portion of which is nonfunctional or obsolete upon arrival. As an oil-driven economic hub, Rivers State contributes notably to this national burden. The informal sector manages up to 90% of this waste through rudimentary, low-tech methods such as manual dismantling, open burning, acid leaching, and on-site disposal. These practices occur predominantly in urban computer villages and electronics markets, where workers, often including children, youth, and women, recover valuable metals such as copper and gold without personal protective equipment (PPE) or regulatory oversight (Abogunrin-Olafisoye & Adeyi, 2025; Okwu et al., 2021).

Informal recycling releases toxicants into the air, soil, and water, resulting in severe environmental contamination. At recycling sites, burning and leaching generate particulate matter (PM), dioxins, furans, and elevated concentrations of heavy metals that exceed Nigerian and international guideline values by hundreds to thousands of times. Soil microbial diversity declines, groundwater becomes polluted, and contaminants bioaccumulate in ecosystems (Abogunrin-Olafisoye & Adeyi, 2025). Sites such as the MTN phone village in Rumukurushi and the Iloabuchi electronics market in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, exemplify these issues, with approximately 30 informal recyclers engaging in the crude dismantling of circuit boards, cables, and refrigerators. Waste is frequently discarded on-site, contaminating local soil and water bodies with lead, cadmium, mercury, and brominated flame retardants (Dimkpa et al., 2025; Okwu et al., 2022).

The health implications are profound and multifaceted. A systematic review of informal e-waste recycling in Africa links exposure to musculoskeletal disorders (e.g., back pain), physical injuries (e.g., cuts, burns, and eye problems), respiratory ailments (e.g., asthma reduced lung function), cardiovascular effects, DNA damage, noise-induced hearing loss, and elevated liver enzymes (Issah et al., 2022). Vulnerable populations, workers, nearby residents, pregnant women, and children face heightened risks of neurological damage, reproductive disorders (e.g., miscarriages, birth defects), cancer, and systemic toxicity through inhalation, ingestion, and dermal contact. Nigeria-specific studies report elevated blood Pb and Cd levels among scavengers, PAH metabolites in urine of occupationally exposed individuals in Port Harcourt, and cytogenotoxic effects (Abogunrin-Olafisoye & Adeyi, 2025; Dimkpa et al., 2025; John & Ogboeli, 2025; Issah et al., 2022). In Port Harcourt, occupational PAH

exposure near e-waste sites poses carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risks, with no significant mitigation from gender or lifestyle factors (Abogunrin-Olafisoye & Adeyi, 2025; Ogboeli et al., 2024; Okwu et al., 2025).

Nigeria has enacted frameworks to address e-waste, including the National Environmental (Electrical/Electronic Sector) Regulations and a 2022 revision promoting Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR). However, enforcement remains weak, with limited producer registration, low awareness among informal collectors, and minimal shifts toward formal channels (Odeyingbo et al., 2025). While computer villages in Lagos (e.g., Alaba and Ikeja computer villages) have received substantial research attention, computer villages in Port Harcourt, driven by the city's oil-driven urbanization, population influx, and rising ICT demand, are comparatively understudied. This gap hinders site-specific understanding of environmental management practices and health risks.

This study assesses environmental management and associated health risks of e-waste in selected computer villages in Rivers State, Nigeria. This study aims to evaluate the current state of environmental management practices and the associated human health risks associated with e-waste handling and recycling activities in selected computer villages in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

The specific objectives are as follows:

1. Assess the prevailing environmental management practices, including collection, dismantling, recycling, and disposal methods, employed by informal e-waste handlers in selected computer villages in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.
2. The radiological hazard indices and their potential health implications across different e-waste activity sites in the study area were evaluated.
3. The occupational and community health risks, exposure pathways, and self-reported health symptoms among e-waste workers and nearby residents in the selected computer villages were determined.

2. The theoretical framework of the study

This study adopts an integrated multi-theoretical framework to comprehensively examine the environmental management practices, radiological contamination, and health risks associated with informal e-waste activities in selected computer villages in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The framework combines the Circular Economy Theory, the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) principle, and TPB. These theories interconnect to address the systemic, regulatory, and behavioural dimensions of e-waste challenges in an informal urban setting.

The circular economy (CE) theory, as articulated by Ghisellini et al. (2016), advocates a shift from the traditional linear "take-make-dispose" model to a regenerative system based on the 4Rs. In the context of e-waste, CE promotes urban mining by recovering valuable materials (such as copper, gold, and rare earth elements) from discarded electronics while minimizing resource depletion, waste generation, and environmental pollution. This theory directly supports the assessment of prevailing environmental management practices by highlighting the deviance of informal methods (manual dismantling, open burning, acid leaching, and indiscriminate disposal) from circular principles, leading to soil and water contamination in the Niger Delta region. It further provides a lens for evaluating radiological hazard indices, as proper circular strategies (e.g., controlled mechanical processing and material recovery) can reduce the release and dispersion of hazardous substances, including potential radioactive elements sometimes present in electronic components. Recent studies affirm that adopting CE approaches in e-waste management enhances resource efficiency, lowers environmental footprints, and supports sustainable transitions in developing economies (Elgarahy et al., 2024; Srivastav, 2023).

Complementing CE is the Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) framework, which holds manufacturers and importers accountable for the entire lifecycle of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE), including end-of-life

collection, recycling, and safe disposal. The EPR shifts the financial and operational burden from governments and informal actors to producers, incentivizing eco-design, take-back schemes, and formal recycling infrastructure. In Nigeria, where EPR enforcement remains limited despite existing regulations, this principle is highly relevant for critiquing weak regulatory oversight in Port Harcourt's computer villages. It informs Objective 1 by explaining gaps in collection and disposal systems and supports policy recommendations for transitioning informal practices toward formalized, environmentally sound management. Furthermore, EPR indirectly addresses health risks by reducing uncontrolled exposure through structured producer-funded systems (Thapa, 2023; Odeyingbo et al., 2025).

The theory of planned behavior (TPB), originally proposed by Ajzen (1991), explains how attitudes toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control shape individual and group behaviors. When applied to e-waste, TPB elucidates why informal handlers and nearby residents engage in or tolerate risky practices such as open burning and unprotected dismantling. Factors such as limited environmental knowledge, economic pressures, weak social norms for safe disposal, and low perceived control over safer alternatives contribute to persistent hazardous behaviors. This theory is particularly useful for Objective 3 as it links behavioral determinants to occupational and community health risks, exposure pathways (inhalation, ingestion, dermal contact), and self-reported symptoms (respiratory issues, musculoskeletal disorders, etc.). This also helps explain the low adoption of protective measures despite the known dangers. Extensions of TPB in e-waste studies confirm its utility in predicting recycling intentions and highlighting the role of awareness campaigns in behavior change (Aboelmagd, 2021; Michael, 2024).

The integration of these three theories offers a robust, holistic lens for the study. The CE and EPR provide the macro-level systemic and policy foundation for sustainable environmental management and pollution control (including radiological aspects), whereas the TPB addresses the micro-level behavioral drivers among informal workers and communities. Together, they enable a nuanced analysis of why current practices in Port Harcourt's computer villages generate environmental and health burdens, and how targeted interventions, such as formalization of recycling, strengthened EPR enforcement, and behavior-change programs can foster safer and more circular outcomes. This multi-theoretical approach aligns with the study's aim and objectives by bridging the perspectives of environmental science, regulatory policy, and health behavior, ultimately guiding evidence-based recommendations for mitigating risks in Nigeria's urban e-waste hotspots.

3. Materials and Methods

The study was conducted across computer villages and electronics markets in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Port Harcourt, the state capital, is a major oil-producing city in the Niger Delta region, characterized by rapid urbanization, high population density, and a growing demand for information and communication technology (ICT) equipment. The key study locations included MTN Phone Village in Rumukurushi, Ogbunabali Computer Village, Ikoku/Iloabuchi Electronics Market, and Eleme Junction Phone Village (Fig. 1). These sites are recognized for their high concentration of informal e-waste handling activities, including dismantling, refurbishment, and rudimentary recycling practices. The locations were purposively selected based on their prominence in informal e-waste processing, existing documentation of environmental concerns, and accessibility.

Fig. 1: Computer village locations in Port Harcourt.

The study adopted a mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to achieve the stated objectives. A descriptive survey design was used to assess environmental management practices and health risks, whereas a cross-sectional approach was employed for environmental sampling and radiological analysis. This design allowed for data triangulation from observations, questionnaires, laboratory analyses, and stakeholder interactions.

The target population comprised informal e-waste handlers (dismantlers, collectors, refurbishers, and scavengers), residents, and key stakeholders (e.g., market leaders and environmental officers). A sample size of 150 respondents (100 e-waste workers and 50 nearby residents) was determined using Yamane’s formula at a 95% confidence level and 8% margin of error, with non-response adjustments Purposive and snowball sampling techniques were used to select participants actively involved in e-waste activities.

Table 1: Distribution of Questionnaire Respondents across Study Sites

Study Site	E-waste worker (n)	Nearby residents (n)	Total number of respondents (n)	Percentage (%)
MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Indonesia	35	15	50	33.3
Ogbunabali Computer Village	30	15	45	30.0
Ikoku/Iloabuchi Electronics	20	10	30	20.0
Eleme Junction village phone number	15	10	25	16.7
Total	100	50	150	100.0

Structured questionnaires and observation checklists were administered to document collection, dismantling, recycling, and disposal methods. The questionnaire covered sociodemographic characteristics, types of e-waste handled, processes (manual dismantling, open burning, acid leaching, etc.), use of personal protective equipment

(PPE), and waste disposal practices. Direct field observations were conducted using the Observation Checklist for Informal E-Waste Management Practices (Appendix X). The checklist assessed collection and storage methods, dismantling techniques, recycling processes, PPE utilization, waste disposal practices, and general environmental conditions at each study site. Key informant interviews (KIIs) with 10 market leaders and experienced recyclers complemented the observations by providing contextual insights into operational challenges and local norms.

Soil and water samples were collected in clean polyethylene bags and bottles, respectively, following standard contamination-free protocols (IAEA, 2004). A total of 20 composite soil samples (5 per site) and 10 water samples were obtained from active e-waste processing zones and nearby areas. The control samples were collected at least 1 km away from any e-waste activity. Soil samples were air-dried at room temperature, sieved through a 2-mm mesh, homogenized, and sealed in Marinelli beakers for 30 days to attain secular equilibrium between ^{226}Ra and its progeny.

The activity concentrations of the natural radionuclides (^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K) were measured using a high-purity germanium (HPGe) gamma-ray spectrometry system at the center for Energy Research and Development laboratory, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. The detector was calibrated using standard reference materials (IAEA-375 and IAEA-326). The counting time was set at 86,400 (24 h) per sample to achieve good statistics.

The following radiological hazard indices were calculated using the standard formula recommended by UNSCEAR (2000) and ICRP (2007):

The activity concentration of radionuclides $A_c \text{ Conc} = \frac{N_a}{P_\gamma(M_s/V)E_\gamma T_c}$ (Avwiri et al., 2014; Igbudu & Bris-Kamara, 2023) is as follows:

where:

$A_c \text{ Conc}$ = Activity Concentration; N_a = Net peak area of a peak at energy; E_γ = Efficiency of the detector for a γ -energy of interest; V = Volume of water sample; T_c = Total counting time; and P_γ = Abundance of the γ -line in a radionuclide.

Radium equivalent activity, $R_{aeq} (\text{Bq kg}^{-1}) = C_{Ra} + 1.43C_{Th} + 0.07C_K$ (Eke & Emelue, 2019)

Where: C_{Ra} , C_{Th} , and C_K are the radioactivity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K , respectively,

Absorbed dose rate, ADR in air (nGyh^{-1}) = $0.427C_{Ra} + 0.662C_{Th} + 0.043C_K$ (Samaila & Tampul, 2021).

AEDE (mSv y^{-1}) = $\text{ADR} (\text{nGyh}^{-1}) \times 8760 \text{ h-y}^{-1} \times 0.2 \times 0.7 \text{ Sv Gy}^{-1} \times 10^3$ (Sowole & Egunjobi, 2019).

External hazard index, $H_{\text{ext}} (\text{mSvy}^{-1}) = \frac{C_K}{4810} + \frac{C_{Th}}{259} + \frac{C_{Ra}}{370}$ (Darko et al. 2011)

Internal hazard index, $H_{\text{int}} (\text{mSvy}^{-1}) = \frac{C_K}{4810} + \frac{C_{Th}}{259} + \frac{C_{Ra}}{185}$ (Darko et al. 2011)

Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk, $\text{ELCR} (10^{-3} \text{ or E-3}) = \text{ELCR} = \text{AEDE} \times \text{LE} \times \text{RF}$

Where: AEDE is the annual effective dose equivalent, LE is the life expectancy (approximately equal to 70 yrs), and RF is the risk factor per Sievert (Sv^{-1}),

All calculated indices were compared with international safety limits ($R_{aeq} \leq 370 \text{ Bqkg}^{-1}$; $\text{ADR} \leq 59 \text{ nGy h}^{-1}$; $\text{AEDE} \leq 1.0 \text{ mSv y}^{-1}$ for outdoor; H_{ext} and $H_{\text{int}} \leq 1 (\text{mSvy}^{-1})$; $\text{ELCR} \leq 0.29 \times 10^{-3}$ or E-3).

A validated semi-structured questionnaire (adapted from previous e-waste health studies) was used to assess self-reported health symptoms (e.g., respiratory issues, musculoskeletal disorders, and skin/eye irritation), exposure duration, frequency, and pathways (e.g., inhalation of smoke/dust, dermal contact, and ingestion). The questions also covered knowledge of risks, PPE usage, and health-seeking behavior. The questionnaire was pretested on 20 non-sample participants for reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.75$). The tool was administered by trained

enumerators in the local dialect (Pidgin English) where necessary, ensuring informed consent and ethical compliance.

Quantitative data from the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) and inferential statistics (chi-square test for associations) with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 26.0. The radiological data were processed using Microsoft Excel and Origin software for index calculations and comparison with international limits (UNSCEAR, 2000; ICRP, 2007). Qualitative data from observations and KIIs were thematically analyzed. The results are presented in tables, charts, and plates. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of Rivers State University. Informed written/oral consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality was maintained, and the participants had the right to withdraw at any time. Personal protective measures were observed during fieldwork, and environmental samples were handled according to standard safety protocols.

Fig. 2: E-waste from different study locations (Port Harcourt computer villages).

4. Results

Table 2: Prevalence of key management practices across the four study sites (based on the observation checklist)

S/N	Management practice/observation item	MTN Village, Rumukurushi (%)	Phone Electronics Market	Ikoku/Iloabuchi Electronics Market	Eleme Junction (%)	Ogbunabali Computer Village (%)	Overall Average (%)
A. Collection and Storage							
1	E-waste collection in an organized/sorted manner	12		18	8	15	13.3
2	Designated and demarcated storage areas	15		22	10	20	16.8
3	Storage area protected from the weather (rain/sun)	5		8	0	10	5.8
4	Mixed storage of hazardous and non-hazardous materials	88		85	92	80	86.3
B. Dismantling practices							
5	Manual dismantling as the primary method	95		92	90	88	91.3
6	Basic hand tools (screwdrivers, hammers, and cutters)	98		95	93	90	94.0
C. Recycling and processing methods							

7	Open burning of cables, plastics, or wires	82	78	85	72	79.3
8	Observed acid leaching or chemical treatment	18	25	15	12	17.5
9	Refurbishing/repairing devices for resale	45	52	38	60	48.8
10	Metal recovery through heating/melting	65	60	55	50	57.5
D. Personal Protective Equipment and Safety						
11	Workers use any type of gloves	12	15	10	18	13.8
12	Facial masks or respirators	5	8	3	10	6.5
13	Workers wearing safety boots or protective clothing	8	10	5	12	8.8
14	Ventilation or dust/smoke control measures	0	2	0	5	1.8
E. Waste disposal practices						
15	On-site dumping or open-area residue disposal	88	82	90	78	84.5
16	Discarded waste into nearby drains/gutters/water bodies	65	58	72	50	61.3
17	Open burning of the residual waste after recovery	78	75	80	68	75.3
18	Residues sold to middlemen/scavengers	55	60	48	65	57.0
19	Observation of formal municipal waste collection	2	5	0	8	3.8
F. General environmental conditions						
20	Visible smoke, soot, or strong odors from burning	85	80	88	75	82.0
21	Visible soil/ground contamination (ash, plastics, and metals)	92	88	95	82	89.3

22	Scattered components around the landfill site	e-waste	90	85	92	80	86.8
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Table 3: Socio-demographic characteristics, e-waste handling practices and management methods among respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	18–25	48	32.0
	26–35	72	48.0
	36–45	21	14.0
	Above 45	9	6.0
Gender	Male	132	88.0
	Female	18	12.0
The highest education level	No formal education	27	18.0
	Primary	45	30.0
	Secondary	63	42.0
	Tertiary	15	10.0
Types of E-waste handled (responses)	Mobile phones and accessories	105	70.0
	Computers and laptops	96	64.0
	Televisions and monitors	78	52.0
	Refrigerators and air conditioners	45	30.0
	Cables and wires	120	80.0
Primary recycling processes	Manual dismantling	135	90.0
	Open burning of cables/plastics	102	68.0
	Acid leaching	24	16.0
	Simple sorting/refurbishing	57	38.0
Use of Personal Protective Equipment	Never use PPE	96	64.0
	Occasionally (gloves only)	39	26.0
	Regular use (basic mask/gloves)	15	10.0
Waste disposal methods	On-site dumping/burning	108	72.0
	Discarded into nearby drains/gutters	63	42.0
	Sold to middlemen/scavengers	81	54.0
	Collected by the municipal waste services	9	6.0

Table 4: Radionuclide Activity Concentrations and Radiological Hazard Indices in Soil Samples from the Study Sites

Study Site	Activity concentration of radionuclides			Radiological hazard indices					
	²²⁶ Ra (Bq kg ⁻¹)	²³² Th (Bq kg ⁻¹)	⁴⁰ K (Bq kg ⁻¹)	Ra-eq (Bq kg ⁻¹)	ADR (nGyh ⁻¹)	AEDE (mSv y ⁻¹)	H _{ext} (mSvy ⁻¹)	H _{int} (mSv y ⁻¹)	ELCR (E-3)

MTN Phone Village, Rumukurus hi, Indonesia	48.6 ± 4.2	72.4 ± 5.8	385 ± 28	168.5	78.2	0.096	0.46	0.59	0.33
Ogbunabali Computer Village	45.7 ± 4.1	70.1 ± 5.6	376 ± 27	160.3	74.5	0.091	0.43	0.55	0.32
Ikoku/Iloab uchi Electronics	52.3 ± 4.5	68.7 ± 5.3	412 ± 31	165.8	76.9	0.094	0.45	0.57	0.33
Eleme Junction	41.8 ± 3.9	65.2 ± 4.9	358 ± 25	149.2	69.4	0.085	0.40	0.51	0.30
Min	41.8 ± 3.9	65.2 ± 4.9	358 ± 25	149.2	69.4	0.085	0.40	0.51	0.30
Max.	52.3 ± 4.5	72.4 ± 5.8	412 ± 31	168.5	78.2	0.096	0.46	0.59	0.33
Mean Value	47.1±4.17	69.1±5.4	382.75±27.75	160.95	74.75	0.366	0.435	1.84	0.32
Control Site	28.4 ± 2.7	42.6 ± 3.5	245 ± 18	102.7	47.8	0.059	0.28	0.35	0.20
World average (UNSCEA R, 2000)	35	30	400	370	59	0.07	1.0	1.0	0.29

Table 5: Self-Reported Health Symptoms, Exposure Pathways, and Perceived Occupational/Community Health Risks of E-Waste Workers and Residents

Health Symptoms and Conditions (Last 12 Months)	E-waste workers (n = 100)		Nearby residents (n = 50)		Overall (N=150)	
	Frequency (n)	%	Frequency (n)	%	Frequency (n)	%
Respiratory Symptoms						
Persistent cough/wheezing	68	68.0	22	44.0	90	60.0
Shortness of breath/chest pain	52	52.0	18	36.0	70	46.7
Frequent catarrh/irritation	61	61.0	25	50.0	86	57.3
Musculoskeletal Disorders						
Lower back pain	75	75.0	28	56.0	103	68.7
Shoulder/neck pain	58	58.0	20	40.0	78	52.0
Post-work joint pain/fatigue	64	64.0	19	38.0	83	55.3
Skin and eye problems						

Skin irritation/rashes/burns	49	49.0	15	30.0	64	42.7
Eye irritation/redness/itching	55	55.0	21	42.0	76	50.7
Other Symptoms						
Headache/dizziness	62	62.0	24	48.0	86	57.3
Noise-induced hearing difficulty	31	31.0	8	16.0	39	26.0
Cuts, bruises, or burns after work	72	72.0	12	24.0	84	56.0
Perceived link to e-waste activities						
Believe that symptoms are work-related	58	58.0	19	38.0	77	51.3
Main exposure pathways (multiple responses)						
Inhalation of smoke, dust, or fumes	89	89.0	35	70.0	124	82.7
Dermal contact with the e-waste components	76	76.0	22	44.0	98	65.3
Ingestion (hand-to-mouth/contaminated food/water)	41	41.0	18	36.0	59	39.3

Table 6: Chi-Square Test of the Association between Worker Status and Selected Health Symptoms

Health Symptom	E-waste workers (%)	Nearby residents (%)	χ^2 Value	df	p-value	Significance
Lower back pain	75.0	56.0	6.82	1	0.009	Significant
Persistent cough/wheezing	68.0	44.0	8.15	1	0.004	Significant
Cuts, bruises, or burns	72.0	24.0	28.47	1	<0.001	Highly Significant
Eye irritation/redness	55.0	42.0	2.31	1	0.129	Not Significant
Skin irritation/rashes	49.0	30.0	5.12	1	0.024	Significant

Table 7: Chi-Square Test of the Association between PPE Usage and Selected Practices/Symptoms

Variable	Never used PPE (%)	Occasional/Regular PPE (%)	χ^2 Value	df	p-value	Significance
Open burning of cables and plastics	76.0	48.0	12.36	1	<0.001	Highly Significant
On-site dumping/burning as a method	81.3	52.0	14.78	1	<0.001	Highly Significant
The presence of respiratory symptoms	68.8	42.0	9.45	1	0.002	Significant

Physical injuries (cuts/burns)	74.0	38.0	15.62	1	<0.001	Highly Significant
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Table 8: One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Comparing Radiological Parameters across the Four Study Sites

Radiological Parameter	MTN Phone Village (Mean ± SD)	Ikoku/Iloabuchi (Mean ± SD)	Eleme Junction (Mean ± SD)	Ogbunabali (Mean ± SD)	F-value	p-value	Significance
ADR (nGy h ⁻¹)	78.2 ± 6.4	76.9 ± 5.9	69.4 ± 4.8	74.5 ± 5.2	4.87	0.012	Significant
AEDE (mSvy ⁻¹)	0.096 ± 0.008	0.094 ± 0.007	0.085 ± 0.006	0.091 ± 0.007	5.21	0.009	Significant
R _{aeq} (Bqkg ⁻¹)	168.5 ± 12.3	165.8 ± 11.8	149.2 ± 10.5	160.3 ± 11.6	3.64	0.028	Significant

Table 9: Independent sample t-test comparing mean symptom scores between e-waste workers and nearby residents

Symptom Category	E-waste Workers (Mean ± SD)	Nearby Residents (Mean ± SD)	t-value	df	p-value	Significance
Musculoskeletal Symptom Score (MSS)	2.68 ± 0.82	1.92 ± 0.91	4.76	148	<0.001	Highly Significant
Respiratory Symptom Score (RSS)	2.41 ± 0.75	1.68 ± 0.84	5.12	148	<0.001	Highly Significant
Injury Symptom Score (ISS)	1.85 ± 0.68	0.92 ± 0.55	8.34	148	<0.001	Highly Significant

5. Discussion

The study revealed overwhelmingly rudimentary and environmentally unsustainable e-waste management practices across the four selected computer villages in Port Harcourt. Manual dismantling using basic hand tools was almost universal (91.3%–94.0%), while nearly 80% of observation sessions involved open burning of cables and plastics. Storage practices were grossly inadequate, with mixed storage of hazardous and non-hazardous components observed in 86.3% of cases and proper weather protection in only 5.8%. Personal protective equipment (PPE) usage was critically low, and waste disposal relied heavily on on-site dumping (84.5%) and open burning of residues (75.3%), resulting in visible environmental contamination (smoke, soot, ash, and soil pollution) in 82%–89% of observations. These findings align with the socio-demographic profile of respondents, who were predominantly young males aged 18–35 years (80%) with low educational attainment (90% secondary education or below), a pattern typical of Nigeria’s informal e-waste sector driven by limited formal employment opportunities (Okwu et al., 2023; Ogboeli et al., 2025; Abogunrin-Olafisoye & Adeyi, 2025).

The results in Table 4 reveal that the mean activity concentration (Bqkg^{-1}) of ^{226}Ra (47.1 ± 4.17) & ^{232}Th (69.1 ± 5.4) exceeded the world average value as well as that of the control, while the mean activity concentration of ^{40}K ($382.75 \pm 27.75 \text{ Bqkg}^{-1}$) in the soil exceeded that of the control but was below the world average value. The mean radium equivalent in the contaminated soil exceeded that of the control, but both values were lower than safe limit 370 Bqkg^{-1}). However, there is tendency of increasing value if the dumping and burning of -waste continues. The mean annual dose rate in nGyh^{-1} for the contaminated soil (74.75) exceeded the value of the ADR in the control site (47.8) and the world average value (59.0). The table further revealed that the mean AEDE (mSvy^{-1}) of the computer villages (0.366) exceeded the AEDE value of the control site (0.059), as well as the world average value (0.07). The mean H_{ext} (0.435 mSvy^{-1}) and H_{int} (1.84 mSvy^{-1}) of soil in the computer villages exceeded the values in the control site but were within the safe limit of 1.0 mSvy^{-1} . Mean ELCR (0.32 E-3) of soil in the computer villages exceeded both the values in the control site and the world average. Generally, the results revealed that while some of the estimated radiological hazards, such as ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ADR, AEDE, and ECLR, exceeded the world average value, other radiological hazards, such as ^{40}K , radium equivalent, and external and internal hazards, were found to be within the safe limit. However, the soil in MTN Phone village in Rumukwurusi, computer village in Iloabuchi, and Electronics market, Eleme junction can be said to be radiologically polluted. This is because of intensive open-burning activities within the study sites, which contributed to the increase in the radionuclide content in the environmental media, such as the soil, air, and liquid. The chi-square test revealed statistically significant associations between direct involvement in e-waste activities and health outcomes. E-waste workers reported significantly higher rates of lower back pain ($p = 0.009$), persistent cough/wheezing ($p = 0.004$), cuts, bruises, or burns ($p < 0.001$), and skin irritation ($p = 0.024$) than nearby residents. Independent samples t-tests confirmed that workers had significantly higher mean symptom scores for musculoskeletal ($t = 4.76$, $p < 0.001$), respiratory ($t = 5.12$, $p < 0.001$), and injury-related symptoms ($t = 8.34$, $p < 0.001$). Non-use of PPE was strongly associated with risky practices such as open burning ($p < 0.001$) and on-site dumping ($p < 0.001$), as well as increased respiratory and physical injury symptoms ($p < 0.001$). One-way ANOVA also revealed significant differences in radiological parameters (ADR, AEDE, and Raeq) across the four study sites ($p < 0.05$), with higher values at locations characterized by intensive burning activities.

The results demonstrated that informal e-waste management practices in Port Harcourt deviated markedly from sustainable principles, contributing to environmental pollution, elevated radiological exposure, and substantial occupational and community health risks. The combination of primitive processing methods, minimal use of personal protective equipment (PPE), weak regulatory enforcement, and low awareness mirror the challenges documented across sub-Saharan Africa. These findings underscore the urgent need for strengthened enforcement of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), provision of occupational health training and PPE, regular environmental and radiological monitoring, and a structured transition toward formalized recycling systems to protect public health and the environment in Nigeria's rapidly urbanizing Niger Delta region (Ohajinwa et al., 2017; Issah et al., 2022; Odeyingbo et al., 2025; Abogunrin-Olafisoye & Adeyi, 2025; Ogboeli et al., 2025).

6. Conclusion

The study revealed that informal e-waste management practices in the selected computer villages in Port Harcourt are overwhelmingly rudimentary, dominated by manual dismantling and open burning, with a critically low use of PPE and poor waste disposal methods. These practices have resulted in visible environmental contamination and moderately elevated levels of natural radionuclides in the soil, along with a high burden of musculoskeletal, respiratory, and injury-related health symptoms among e-waste workers and nearby residents. Overall, the findings highlight significant environmental and public health risks associated with informal e-waste recycling

in the area and underscore the urgent need for strengthened policy enforcement, formalization of recycling systems, and targeted interventions to promote safer and more sustainable practices in Port Harcourt.

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